

**TWO CENTERS OF VOLCANIC ACTIVITY IN THE GUZOR MOUNTAINS AND
THEIR MINERAL SIGNS**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7177107>

A.S. Ganiev

*National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulug'bek, Faculty of Geology and
Geoinformation Systems 5A 140806 - master, majoring in geological surveys and
prospecting for mineral deposits.*

Annotation: *The Zarmas and Suluvkol ore targets of colchedan-polymetallic mineralization in the Yakkabog field are considered in the article. information on the mineral composition and genesis of mineral targets is given.*

Key words: *Zarmas and Suluvkol mine targets, prospecting, hydrothermal-metasomatic processing, gold, pyrite, arsenopyrite, copper, polymetals, Yakkabog Mountains.*

V.M. Biryukov (1952-57), A.V. Golovchenko (1982-85), E.S. Tsmeyrek, U.K. Arifov (1999-2002), U.K. Arifov (2003-2006). V. Suluvkol ore target was discovered by Andreev [1,4,6,7].

The Zarmas and Suluvkol ore deposits, consisting of gold-silver mineralization located in rhyolite tuffs ("Zarmas" series) and effusive rocks ("Chinarsoy" series), are the most characteristic objects that determine the metallogenic nature of Yakkabog volcano-tectonic structure.

According to the facies features and interpretation of space images, the Chorti dome occupies the location of the mouth of the Chorti-Valiyak volcanic apparatus. It is spatially connected with the Vauri mine target.

The Chorti dome and its immediate surroundings are complexed with dyke-like and irregularly shaped bodies of Permian-age felsites and granite-porphyrries, indicating long-term activity of the volcanic center.

These rocks are classified under the Permian complex because they break all previous geological formations, they have an unweathered appearance, they have not experienced orogenic dynamometamorphism, they are characterized by high alkalinity in the potassium series characteristic of this complex, and they are similar to the formations in the south of Surkhontov. Extrusive-effusive facies Chorti-Valiyak volcanic apparatus consists of extrusive domes, from which lava flows and clastic lavas erupted, and extrusive dykes.

Two domes are distinguished: Chorti and Uvolsok. Chorti bortish dome is about 1 km across and consists of trachyrhyolite-dacite porphyries. Domes of the second order are also observed. The central part of the root or the bottom of the channel is filled with rhyolites of the final phase of extrusion. The dome was formed by injection of near-surface sublayered

trachyrhyolite-dacite lavas in a northerly direction. The rocks are indistinctly fluid, columnar shape is not visible. Apophyses of lavas penetrated the adjacent tuff mass.

The Uvolsok thrust dome is located 0.5-1.5 km south of the Chorti thrust dome, and is up to 2 km across. Rhyolite and rhyolite-dacite porphyries are composed of lava flows and lava breccias. Most of the lava breccias are considered explosive, characterized by fluidity, the main mass is felsitic and distributed as flows. In this case, the "explosive" breccias also exploded, but did not occur in the volcanic chamber during the explosion, but in a closed system at a certain depth inside the chamber before the flow or rupture.

Picture. 1-Zarmas, 2-Suluvkol structures

The main mass of these rocks includes crystalloclasts, vitroclasts, and even fragments of volcanic glass. A spherical separation of explosive lava breccias is observed in the western part of the dome. These formations are unique and allow to divide the extrusive facies into an independent subfacies.

In the northern part of this dome, a smaller secondary dome with a clear columnar separation of rhyolites is observed, which belongs to the second phase of extrusions.

In the southeastern part of the dome, there is a throat-feeder channel, which is filled with lava breccias with clear fluidity. The described extension is complicated by dike and stock bodies of late igneous rocks.

There is a spatial and possibly paragenetic association of gold-silver mineralization with centers of volcanic activity.

Zarmas mine badge

The Zarmas Mine target is located southwest of the center of Kyzildara volcanic activity and is located within a well-defined caldera discontinuity zone. This structure consists of a 300-400m-thick fold zone in the north-west direction and is connected by a system of semi-ring faults on the north-west edge. In the immediate vicinity of the mine target, Lower Permian Luchob complex explosive breccia bodies are exposed on the surface, which are specialized for gold mineralization.

The mine-control zone is a long-lived Early Carboniferous structure along the northwestern fault-synvolcanic caldera discontinuity. Its volcanogenic deposits have clear

traces of fumarole reworking, and the late Permian magmatic complex is filled with bodies of diabase and andesite porphyrites. The warp zone is clearly represented by a belt of hydrothermally altered rocks in the north-west direction.

The interior of this structure is filled with a subparallel seam zone of brecciation, mylonitization and schistization ranging from 10-15m to 25-30m in thickness. Zones of brecciation, mylonitization, and schistization and subparallel rift systems form an interconnected system with a relatively low (50-55°) southwest dip.

The mine target area is characterized by a north-easterly fracture zone, a transverse fault system flanked by linear quartz stockworks.

The intersection of longitudinal (north-west) and transverse (north-east) faults led to the formation of nodules with maximum tectonic disintegration of adjacent rocks and maximum intensity of hydrothermal-metasomatic processing.

The adjacent rocks at the Zarmas mine target belong to the mainly pyroclastic facies of the Middle Vakhshivar sub-suite of approximately Lower Carboniferous age (aero-marine peplod facies). Rhyolite (rhyolito-dacite) tuffs in the immediate vicinity of the mining target are silt-psammitic to fine psephytic.

Leech target structure

The Hertzian structure of the Suluvkol deposit is determined by its location on the northern flank of the Kyzildara paleovolcanic syncline, which is complicated by 2-3 order isoclinal folds and a thrust-thrust zone. In this zone, selective shale formation, layering of adjacent layers and inter-layer and layer shifts, cutting diagonal cracks and folding of rock layers are observed. It stretches for 2 km from east to west along the entire area of the mine. In general, the zone consists of cataclastic or shale rocks.

In the area of the mining target, a number of earth cracks have been identified that are transverse and diagonal to the direction of the rocks. Usually they have the character of discontinuity, discontinuity-displacement (in north-east, north-west and submeridional directions).

The found ore bodies have irregular, lenticular shapes, vary in thickness, and lie subconformably to the adjacent rocks. Variation of lenticular shape and thickness along the direction is determined by the nature of rock deformation and the morphology of the quartz porphyry contact zone. The nature of mineralization in the mineralized zone is unstable. Thick sections with rich ore alternate with zones of weak sulphide mineralization.

Most of the gold is found in arsenopyrite. Gold particles are elongated, vein-shaped, drop-shaped, irregular, rarely isometric.

Gold tellurides (calaverite AuTe₂) are a common inclusion in galena. The shape is approximately isometric, slightly elongated, the borders are usually flat, xenomorphic appendages are also found. Sizes range from 0.00n to 0.0n mm.

LITERATURE:

1. Arapov V.A., Mikhailov V.V. i dr. Paleozoic volcano-tectonic Koltsevaya structure Yugo-zapadnyx otrogov Gissara // Uzb. geol. journal. - 1971. - No. 1.
2. Pankratev P.V. O rudoproyavleniyax kolchedanno-polymetallicheskogo tipa yugo-zapadnyx otrogov Hissarskogo hrebta (Yujnyy Uzbekistan) // Voprosy geologii Sredney Azii i Kazakhstan. - Tashkent, 1963.
3. Arapov V.A., Mikhailov V.V. i dr. Paleozoic volcano-tectonic Koltsevaya structure Yugo-zapadnyx otrogov Gissara // Uzb. geol. journal. - 1971. - No. 1.
4. Pankratev P.V., Mikhailova Yu.V. Kolchedanno-polimetallicheskoe orudneniya Yuzhnogo Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Science, 1971.
5. Golovchenko A.V., Volkodav V.I. Report on the topic: "Formational-facies analysis of the volcanic formation of the main rudny field of the south-western outcrop of the Hissar ridge with the creation of a map scale 1:25000 in 1986". Fondy Kashkadarinskoy GRE.
6. Iskhakov K.G., Pankratev P.V. Otchet o rezultatax poiskovo-revizionnyx rabot na med v Yakkabagskikh gorax provennyx v 1971-73 godax (Otchet Kuldarinskoy PRP po rabotam 1971-73 g.g.). Fondy Kashkadarinskoy GRE
7. Klibley G.H., Baymukhamedov I.D., Ibragimov R.M. Otchet po teme "Metasomatizm i orudnenie na kolchedanno-polymetallicheskikh mestorojdeniyax Yuzhnogo Uzbekistana", 1979g. Fondy GGP "Samarkand Geology".
8. Tsmeyrek E.S., Arifov U.K. Otchet o rezultatax operejyushchix spetsializirovannyx poiskovyx rabot na zoloto i dobie poleznye skopaemye na Zarmasskoy ploshchadi v Yakkabagskikh gorakh v 1999-2002 g.g. Fondy Kashkadarinskoy GRE.